

CONTENTS

Dutch methodology of risk assessment for contaminated soils

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ABSTRACT

Since 1994 a new Soil Protection Act has become effective in the Netherlands. It uses Intervention values, based on potential risk of contaminated soil or ground water for humans or the ecosystem. The methodology is described in detail. If an Intervention value is exceeded, one has to define the urgency of a remediation. That must be done by means of a risk assessment that defines actual risk for humans and the ecosystem, by taking site specific information into consideration. A (global) critical review of the Dutch system is given. Finally, the Dutch method is compared with a German technique (in development). From this it is concluded, that international harmonization is needed on the parameters and toxicological data being used in the different models.

CONCEPT

In the Netherlands recently a new method for assessing risk of contaminated soil has been developed (VROM, 1994). The procedure is to be used by regulators to manage and prioritise contaminated sites for remediation. The method is based on a scientific approach using risk analysis, including exposure assessment and human and ecotoxicological data.

Its philosophy is, that soil contamination is not tolerable, if risks for humans or ecosystem are likely to occur that exceeds the maximal tolerable risk levels. From this starting point the system follows. One has to define maximal tolerable risk (MTR) for man and ecosystem, and to calculate at what levels of the contamination in soil, the MTR is exceeded.

Humans

The maximal tolerable risk level for humans in the Netherlands is said to be determined by the Tolerable Daily Intake (TDI). The TDI can be estimated from epidemiological studies on human toxicology, or derived at from toxicological studies with experimental animals (WHO/EURO, 1987). It describes the maximal tolerable exposure on a daily basis. Now one has to calculate the exposure of humans, coming from a contaminated site. Therefore, exposure was estimated from direct contact by soil ingestion, dermal application, and inhalation of particles and gaseous phase of chemicals, and indirect contact through ingestion of contaminated vegetables and drinking water after permeation of conduit pipes. By use of physicochemical models, such as the Mackay model and the Jury model, one can predict from initial concentrations of chemicals in soil or ground water the concentration in the various contact media for humans, relevant for the exposure routes. By means of the contribution of the various exposure pathways, using well accepted parameters describing human exposure, one can calculate the total daily intake of a chemical at a contaminated site. The human toxicological intervention value is said to be equal to the concentration of a compound in soil or ground water, that gives an intake as large as the TDI. For this purpose an exposure model CSOIL was developed by the National Institute of Public Health and Environmental Protection (Van den Berg, 1991). A schematic review is shown in figure 1. The model is both conceptually and numerically comparable with the HESP model (ECETOC, 1990).

Ecosystem

For estimating risk of soil contamination for the ecosystem, a statistical approach was used, describing concentrations in soil in relation to a percentage of species of the ecosystem at risk (Van Straalen and Denneman, 1989; Denneman and Van Gestel, 1990). The median value, with potential 50% at risk was assigned to the ecotoxicological intervention value. The latter figure is referred to as the Hazardous Concentration for 50% of the species: HC₅₀.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the submodels and exposure routes in the CSOIL model (Van den Berg, 1991)

INTERVENTION VALUE

By combining the human and ecotoxicological intervention value, the Dutch intervention value was set (Van den Berg and Roels, 1991). As a consequence of this method, exceeding of an intervention value is similar to a potential risk for humans or the ecosystem, as it includes all possible exposure routes for humans, and as the HC₅₀ was derived from an all around ecosystem.

Actual risk

On second thought, exceeding does not imply an actual risk per sé. The latter is depending on the site specific information: what exposure routes are actually in effect? What ecosystem is supposed to exist there? To settle that question it is decided that one should perform a risk analysis for humans and ecosystem, for the chemicals in soil and ground water that exceed the intervention value, by including site specific information. If it shows an actual risk, remediation is urgently needed.

By setting up a complete set of rules, the Dutch environmental regulators do now describe how to conduct a risk analysis. These are written down in the new Soil Protection Act, and referred to as the "Urgentiesystematiek" (System for urgency). It orders to describe the size of a contamination, and the representative concentration in the bulk. These data are to be evaluated in combination with a scenario, describing the actual use of the site (industrial, housing and others). The CSOIL model is recommended for estimating the actual human exposure, whereas another set of rules is given to define the actual risk for ecosystem. Spreading is evaluated by a geohydrological model, including a mass transfer (Koolenbrander, 1995). In daily practice, the risk assessment can now be made using a computer model (as developed by the authors of this paper). Input in the model includes the concentration of the compounds in soil or ground water, and site specific information. The advantage of this approach is the consistency in assessment of different sites. The results can then be used to compare the various sites, that are to be remediated, and one can set priorities.

POSSIBILITIES AND RESTRICTIONS OF THE CSOIL MODEL

The model does predict concentrations in contact media, and estimates exposure accordingly. Human exposure data, such as ventilation rate and amount soil ingested per day

can easily be changed to adjust the model to site specific information. The predicted concentration in contact media, such as inside air, or levels in contaminated vegetables, however does depend on the underlying submodels. As the correctness of some of the submodels is to be questioned, additional analysis in the contact media is often strongly to be advised. But the outcome of the model prediction gives a good indication what analysis is to be preferred. The model can then be used again for a risk assessment, after including the data of concentrations determined in contact media.

Another critical remark is, that the intervention values do not take background exposure from other sources into account. It is equal to the total tolerable exposure from contaminated soil, and therefore underestimates the actual total exposure at a site. Besides, secondary exposure from food that is contaminated at the site is also not included in the CSOIL model at the present. And, as the intervention values were derived from life time exposure, it will underestimate actual risk for young children. These, and other critical notes are more extensively reviewed by Nijhof and Theelen (1994). Regulatory adjustments at that point is hoped for in the near future.

Using an exposure model such as CSOIL creates opportunities to calculate site specific levels in soil that can be tolerated by specific use, like vegetable gardens, housing, or industrial sites. It must be stated however, that a check on the model predictions by additional analysis in contact media, as described in the previous section, is not possible in most cases. A critical look at the different submodels within CSOIL remains therefore essential, and improvements of the model must be implemented on a regular basis.

It must be emphasized, that a risk assessment for humans by means of a model, such as CSOIL, is actually just an exposure assessment. Only, because the Dutch environmental policy does not accept an exceeding of a TDI, one could talk about a "risk" assessment. The model predictions give not information on possible health problems for those that are exposed. From a toxicological point of view one can state that adverse effects can not be excluded to humans when exceeding a TDI. In these cases, a closer examination of the exposed humans, focused on possible health problems is needed, using medical tests and biological monitoring in blood or other relevant parameters.

REMARKS ON THE ECOTOXICOLOGICAL METHOD

The Dutch method, using HC₅₀ values does only give some insight into the potential problems for ecosystems. The proposal in the system is to define an actual risk for an ecosystem by relating surface area and function. This is scientifically grounded by the ecotoxicological concepts, such as pyramidal food webs. As the ecotoxicological intervention value is derived from a theoretical "complete" ecosystem, it suggests that every ecosystem can be expected on a sufficient large area. It is well known however, that different types of vegetation and their fauna are relying on the soil type, and other abiotic parameters, such as climate and ground water levels. It can be expected, that critical levels in soil or ground water may differ substantially for the different types of vegetation. Therefore one can not use the present Dutch system to calculate tolerable levels in different types of ecosystems, to be used as endpoint for remediation.

RISK ASSESSMENT IN OTHER COUNTRIES

Except for the Netherlands is a method of risk assessment of contaminated soil, operational described in detail, known for Germany and the United Kingdom. They too use the concept of a risk assessment as a discriminator for need and urgency of remediation. The German model (UMS) however is still under development, and not yet completed for regulatory use (Doetsch et al., 1994). In the UK also a risk based approach is followed. Concentrations in soil are to be compared to "action" values. These action values are dependent from the after-use, contradictory to the Dutch approach. The trigger values are calculated by the computer model called CLEA (Contaminated Land Exposure Assessment). This model is similar to the CSOIL and UMS model using the concept of calculation of human exposure from contaminated soil and acceptable daily exposure. As for CSOIL, the CLEA model can be used to estimate human exposure at a site, and is suited for assessment of actual risks. If needed it takes background exposure into account. In contrast to the CSOIL and UMS model, CLEA uses probability density functions for the site specific and population specific parameters, whereas the CSOIL and UMS model only use fixed data. A Monte Carlo submodel is included in CLEA for testing sensitivity of output to the various input values and model assumptions (Ferguson and Denner, 1993). Other countries, such as the USA, do also use the concept of risk for humans and ecosystems for evaluating contaminated soil, but the concept is not well documented. Most European countries however have no clear described methodology at all.

The Dutch CSOIL model was compared with the German UMS model. Comparison with the CLEA model is considered for the near future. From the results the following conclusions can be drawn. Numerical output may deviate substantially. The UMS includes background exposure, and discriminates between anthropogenic and geogenic sources. Besides, differences in the various submodels result in different concentrations in contact media. Besides, using different exposure parameters outcome varies also. However, as both countries do show differences in human (social) behaviour and geologic characteristics, these different model predictions may demonstrate relevant distinctions. One can also notice major differences for the numerical assignment of the TDIs for the same chemicals in both models. As these are derived from an international scientific data base, it is rather surprisingly that different group of toxicologist did suggest different proposals. It is highly dubious, that a compound shows another toxic potency in another country. Harmonization on this is urgently needed.

CONCLUSIONS

It can be concluded, that as Intervention values are arrived at from potential risk for humans or the ecosystem, they are good indicators for more thorough investigation on a soil contamination at a site.

The Dutch methodology for risk assessment of soil contamination to define an actual risk is well described, scientific sound, and reproducible. Especially the CSOIL model for assessing risk for humans is a useful tool: in spite of its restrictions, it offers good insight on the relevant exposure routes and can be used to manage additional analysis. However, assessment of risk for humans and the ecosystem is to be used by regulators, and does not predict actual health problems. The CSOIL model can also be used for calculating end point for remediation, and remaining risk by various measures to be taken, in relation to different type of soil use. The results do however depend on selection of exposure data, and toxicological standards, and standardized data is to be preferred. The method of risk assessment of the ecosystem, based on ecotoxicological intervention values is not suited for calculation site specific concentrations with tolerable risk.

Comparing the Dutch CSOIL model and the German UMS model shows that results may deviate due to the selection of exposure data. Discussion on these data is needed to see what can be explained from real differences in both countries, and what from debatable

differences in model assumptions. Large differences appeared to exist for human toxicological figures. The latter calls for international harmonization.

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